

APPROVED by
Order No V-251 of the Chairman of the
Research Council of Lithuania
of 12 June 2024

Action Plan for the Application of the CoARA Principles in the Activities of the Research Council of Lithuania (2024-2028)

No	Task	Brief description of the task	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028
I. RCL's readiness to implement the CoARA principles							
1.1.	Assess the coherence of the RCL's strategic activity directions and priorities, the strategic plan and the CoARA principles.	1) Continuously review and update the strategic activity directions, priorities and the plan to align it with the CoARA principles. 2) Identify strategic challenges related to the application of the CoARA principles. 3) Identify solutions for challenges and include them in the CoARA Action Plan.	x		x	x	x
1.2.	Provide resources necessary for the implementation of the CoARA actions.	1) Provide resources for the implementation of the CoARA Action Plan, including training for the RCL experts and applicants.		x	x	x	x
1.3.	Develop the research culture and research activity assessment practices based on the principles of qualitative assessment.	1) Communicate with the RCL, experts, Lithuanian research communities, other CoARA institutions and the public on the application of the CoARA principles and changes in the research culture. 2) Improve competences of the RCL applicants and experts in preparing and assessing proposals in line with the CoARA principles.	x	x	x	x	x
1.4.	Monitor the implementation of the CoARA Plan.	1) Monitor the implementation of the CoARA Action Plan according to the parts provided for therein.		x	x	x	x
II. Improving the assessment of R&D performance of research and higher education institutions and their departments							

2.1	Improve the expert assessment methodology in line with the CoARA principles.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Analyse good practices in expert assessment of R&D activities in selected foreign countries. 2) Develop and implement criteria for the proper evaluation of interdisciplinary research papers. 3) Review the content and format of the institution's self-assessment. 4) Reflect on the implementation of the principle of transparency in the provision of institutional data for evaluation: publication of the institutions' self-analysis reports (except sensitive data). 	x	x	x	x						
2.2.	Improve the formal evaluation methodology in line with the CoARA principles.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Consider all components of formal evaluation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • research papers; • international projects; • contracts with economic operators. 2) Identify those formal evaluation components that could be modified to move towards qualitative evaluation, taking into account the incentive funding based on this evaluation; 3) Consult research and higher education institutions and associations; 4) Specify the timeframes of possible amendments, what legal acts and how should be amended. 	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
2.3	Consider the data necessary for the expert assessment and formal evaluation methodologies updated on the basis of the CoARA principles. Initiate collection and processing of new data.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Identify what data and how could be collected and processed taking into account the features and capacities of existing databases; 2) Update the documents governing the collection of relevant data from research and higher education institutions. 					x	x	x	x	x	x

2.4.	Formulate proposals for possible changes to the R&D assessment system in relation to other assessments carried out in Lithuania.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Assess how the CoARA principles affect the assessment of doctoral studies by the RCL. 2) Consider other possible linkages. 		x		x		x		x		x
2.5.	Formulate proposals on the need to update the relevant legal acts and initiate their updating.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Consider and initiate, as appropriate, amendments to the Law on Research and Higher Education related to the application of the CoARA principles; 2) Consider and initiate, as appropriate, amendments to legal acts of the MESS (assessment descriptions, funding procedures) and related changes; 3) Consider and initiate, as appropriate, related amendments to legal acts, procedures, regulations of the RCL. 		x		x		x		x		x
III. Improving the evaluation of research projects												
3.1.	Systematically improve the evaluation of research projects in line with the CoARA principles.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Review the proposal forms for the RCL measures, identify possible non-compliances with the CoARA principles and provide guidance for their improvement. 2) Review the criteria for evaluation the RCL measures, identify the criteria that may not be in line with the CoARA principles and provide guidance for their improvement. 		x	x							
3.2.	Review the proposal, scientific report and their evaluation forms of the researcher groups projects (RGPs)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Assess the experience of the proposal and its evaluation forms used in the RGP Call XIII: upon approval of the call results conduct surveys of the principal investigators of projects selected for funding and peer review panels, as well as of the RCL's administrative staff, observers appointed by committees, and the staff of project management units of implementing institutions, summarise results, and propose possible improvements to the forms. 			x	x	x	x	x			

3.3.	Consider the effectiveness of application of the CoARA principles.	1) Once a year, evaluate different types of practices of the RCL measures in relation to the evaluation of proposals and their reports: determine the evaluation method (ex-post evaluation, survey, desk review, etc.), summarise the evaluation results, suggest aspects to be modified (in terms of documentary forms, internal regulations, etc.). Consider other possibilities, methods and frequency of feedback between applicants, experts, institutions and the RCL.		x		x		x		x		
		2) In the context of ex-post evaluations of measures, also consider compliance with the CoARA principles or practices and expertise of their application.		x	x	x	x	x				
3.4.	Formulate proposals for amendments to the Lithuanian legal acts pertaining to the assessment of research projects.	1) Evaluate both internal legal acts of the RCL and external regulations approved by other entities for adherence to the CoARA principles (e.g., the doctoral (PhD) programme regulations, the description of the procedure for the implementation of the competition-based doctoral (PhD) programme, the description of the procedure for the provision of support to doctoral (PhD) students), 2) Suggest possible amendments, initiate discussion with the legislators of the above mentioned legal acts.		x	x	x						
IV. Improving the assessment of researcher competences												
4.1.	Accumulate good practices of institutions in assessing researcher competences and share them with the research community.	1) Conduct a survey of research and higher education institutions. 2) Analyse the responses received and make recommendations.				x	x	x				
4.2.	Initiate amendments to the LHER on mandatory	1) Summarise the survey results, draw on the European experience, identify shortcomings						x	x			

	competences of researchers in line with the CoARA principles.	in the assessment of researchers, and initiate the necessary amendments to the RL Law on Higher Education and Research (LHER).										
4.3.	Share experiences in assessing the competences of researchers in line with the CoARA principles for evaluating R&D activities.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Systematise experiences in assessing researcher competences and develop good practice guidelines. 2) Share good practice guidelines for assessing researcher competences with those responsible for the assessment of research projects. 3) Share good practice guidelines for assessing researcher competences with those responsible for the assessment of doctoral studies. 4) Share good practice guidelines for assessing researcher competences with those responsible for assessing activities of research and higher education institutions. 				x		x		x		x